

The role of composition of the educational subject in the process of figurative thinking

Ibatova Nigora Istamovna

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Dotsent of the Department of Music and Fine Arts

Annotation. Following article deals with the role of the subject of composition in the development of artistic skills. We can include here figurative thinking, creative thinking, teaching on creative approach to the life impressions, enriching memory and depicting these impressions, figurative form, as well as visual memory of learners`.

Key words: Image, absolute, organic, inorganic, principle, object, picture plane, image elements, harmony, rhythm, principle, synthesis, structure, methodology.

As we know, mankind naturally learns everything from nature. However, what about a naturalist? It is not as simple as we know, but complex, multi-faceted, limitless, which a person cannot know everything at an absolute level, indeed only strives to know. The result of this aspiration leads to the creation of innovations in science and art.

When a person sees the vision of nature, he or she supports the principles of the structure of organic and inorganic nature, and through creative thinking, he or she expresses the subject and its manifestations in the most vivid visual state. This chosen situation is "composition", and it arouses people's emotions, directs them to certain ideas and imaginations.

Composition is derived from the Latin word "compositio", which means "to compose", "to place", "to create". It is characteristic of all types of composition art.

For example, painting composition means placing image elements on the plane of the picture in such a way as to allow the optimal and strongest expression of the intended idea. In other words, composition means bringing separate parts into a logical whole. In order to understand composition more fully, let's bring to mind a great "composition" in nature - miraculous naturalness. We can also observe that the individual elements are located in a certain order. They are interconnected and create a complete harmony in the world of plants and animals. Any simple plant is made up of small pieces. Together, they form a certain shape and lead to a vision that is seen as a whole.

Composition belongs to all types of art. Elements of composition are also used in architectural constructions, works of art, sculptures and paintings, film and theater productions. The principles of unity and division, symmetry and rhythm are manifested in different types of art. The mutual adaptation of these principles creates synthetic arts. Dramaturgy, cinema, television, and circus arts are examples of this.

When talking about the aspects of the concept of "composition", it can be said that it is based on the specific characteristics of different arts, and its content and level of use are different in each of them. For example, in the art of music, the issues of composition are quite limited, they are described in a general plan, and only in mixed cases are the details combined with each other. In literature, the elements are used on the basis of a complete content, and the specific location of certain material in the text is required or it is assumed that the content is filled in a row.

As for the position of the concept of composition in visual arts, there are still many uncertainties in this field. The reason is that the theory of composition still needs to be regulated. Although there are different views in this field, composition needs to be created in a deep and special way as a separate theory that does not deal with art theory or aesthetics. This theory

should be created as a "theory of composition" as a part of the theory of art studies, and it should express the composition, problems, and terms of fine art in a very clear way.

We find the first concepts of composition in Brockhaus and Yefron's dictionary. Based on the analysis of the best works of art, only some rules are shown. It pays great attention to integrity as the main aspects of the composition. That is, "integrity serves to express the idea of the artist" – as there is emphasized.

According to V.A.Favorsky opinion: "One of the qualities of composition can be as follows: striving for composition in art means to perceive, see and describe different spatialities and different temporalities as a whole. To bring the image to view as a whole is composition".

K. F. Yuon believes that "a painting should be a structure in a composition, which is divided into planes with its parts, and also divided into a structure arising from plane factors".

Art critics L.F. Yegin and B.A. Uspensky indicated that "... the central issue of composition is the point of view" and "... the issue of the point of view in a painting appears first of all as a matter of perspective".

According to Ye.A.Kibrik opinion: "Integrity is not only a necessary quality of composition, but also one of the main laws of composition, and it is found through the constructive idea".

N.N. Volkov calculates the composition as follows: "The composition of works of fine art is the main artistic form of fine art, it combines other forms as a whole, individual elements combine to form a whole, which cannot be taken away or changed, artistic it is impossible to add to the image without harming it, and this integrity lies in an inseparable unity with the ideological purpose of the work". He believes that "structure is more general, and construction is seen as a type of structure".

The educational subject of composition aims to: provide knowledge on the composition of fine art, educate creativity, develop creative abilities, and increase cognitive activity. In order to successfully implement this goal, it is planned to conduct a number of educational activities with students under the guidance of the teacher.

The tasks of the subject of composition are as follows:

1. Forming students to fight for a broad, universal worldview, the idea of society development.
2. Cultivating artistic taste, artistic aesthetic culture in students.
3. Cultivating students' artistic abilities such as figurative thinking, creative thinking, and visual memory.
4. Studying the history of the creation of the work, the process and stages of its creation along with the analysis of the compositional construction of the works.
5. To acquire knowledge and skills in the analysis of works of art in terms of compositional issues, and to use them in their independent creations.
6. Students study the theoretical foundations of composition as a subject and methods of teaching it.
7. To study with students the theoretical foundations of composition in relation to the historical development and practical creation of the work of art.
8. In order to develop artistic observation in students:
 - a) to teach students to observe the surrounding environment from an artist's point of view with a special purpose;

b) teaching to approach life impressions creatively, enriching the memory and depicting these impressions in a creative, figurative way;

c) drawing drafts, sketches, sketches based on artistic observation of students, carrying out various exercises and researches from nature, finding situations of imagery from nature, performing composition works.

9. Teaching to create a composition with a figurative conclusion in its content.

10. To acquire compositional skills, to be able to use this knowledge and skills appropriately in educational and independent work.

11. Preparing future artists-pedagogues for independent creative and pedagogical activities in the field of composition.

Practical-auditory works are carried out in the following order:

a) introductory interview and receiving assignments;

b) practical exercise;

c) discussion and conclusion of the completed work.

During the study, students also perform independent homework on composition. There are different forms of homework, including:

a) work on a composition sketch;

b) observing the environment and life depending on the topic of the practical assignment;

c) making sketches, drafts and sketches on the subject;

d) performing exercises for developing compositional thinking (sensing color palette, finding compositional integrity);

e) getting acquainted with new materials related to composition tasks;

f) on the basis of literature and museum materials, it can be, for example, the study of household life and the character of the hero of the time.

Composition is not only a separate subject, but also combines many disciplines. In addition, the subject of composition is closely related to aesthetics, ethics, history of art. The concept of universal beauty forms the methodological basis of the composition.

Through the history of art, they get acquainted with the works of great artists. At the same time, the subject of composition is closely related to the teaching methodology of fine arts. The reason is that it is necessary for creative artists to know the methods of teaching composition.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati

1. G'.M. Abduraxmonov "Kompozitsiya asoslari" Toshkent, 2010 y.
2. E. Jabborov "Kompozitsiya" Qarshi, 2019 y.
3. A.Turdaliyev "Kompozitsiya" Toshkent, 2003 y.
4. Ibatova, Nigora. "QALAMTASVIR FANINI O 'QITISHDA TALABALARNING BADIY-OBRAZLI TAFAKKURINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Академические исследования в современной науке* 2.27 (2023): 57-63.
5. Ибатова, Нигора Истамовна. "TALABLARNING TASVIRIY YARATUVCHANLIK, IJODKORLIK POTENTIALLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH: Ibatova Nigora Istamovna Buxoro davlat pedagogika institute "Musiq va tasviriy san'at" kafedrasida o'qituvchisi." *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал* 2 (2023): 261-265.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

6. Ибатова, Нигора Истамовна, and Камолиддин Жаҳонгир ўғли Ҳақимов. "XIX АСР АНГЛИЯ ТАСВИРИЙ САНЪАТИДА МАНЗАРА ЖАНРИ." *ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI* 1 (2022): 101-105.
7. 8.Istamovna, Ibatova Nigora. "Pedagogical approaches to the development of artistic thinking of students." *International conference on multidisciplinary science*. Vol. 1. No. 5. 2023.
8. Khakimova, G. A., Azimova, M. B., Tuksanova, V. R., & Ibatova, N. I. (2021). Didactic principles in teaching fine arts. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol*, 27(2).
9. Mamurova D. I., Ibatova N. I., Badieva D. M. The importance of using the keys-stadi innovative educational technology method in training the image module of geometric shapes //Scientific reports of Bukhara State University. – 2020. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 335-338.
10. Ibatova N. DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'ARTISTIC-PICTURE THINKING IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF PAINTING //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. B2. – С. 163-167.
11. Istamovna I. N., Maxmudovna M. R. Landscape Genre in Russian Fine Art of the XIX Century //Innovative Science in Modern Research. – 2023. – С. 218-222.
12. Istamovna I. N., Rakhimovich R. S. The Use of Innovative Technologies in Developing The Creative Potential of The Students in The Fine Arts //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2019. – Т. 7.
13. Khodjayeva, Nodira. "THE URGENCY OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN PROSPECTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING." *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры* 3.5 (2023): 77-80.
14. Ходжайева N. S. et al. HTML ELEMENTLARI VA ATRIBUTLAR //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 115-119.
15. Abdullayev¹ S. F., Abdullayev S. S. TRANSLATION OF CULTURAL VALUES IN THE ARTISTIC HERITAGE OF TRADITIONAL APPLIED ARTS OF BUKHARA.
16. Абдуллаев С. С. РОЛЬ СРЕДНЕВЕКОВОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ ВОСТОКА В СОЗДАНИИ СЮЖЕТОВ МИНИАТЮРЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ //Inter education & global study. – 2023. – №. 2. – С. 100-108.
17. Jurayevich J. K., Sayfullayevich A. S. THE UNIQUE OF BUKHARA JEWS IN THE DYE INDUSTRY AND WEAVING CRAFT //Euro-Asia Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 48-53.
18. Sayfullayevich A. S. CHALLENGES OF TRAINING FINE ARTS TEACHERS IN THE PRESENT //International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics. – 2023. – С. 348-353.
19. Abdullaev S., Mamatov D. Pedagogical foundations in the teaching of folk arts and crafts of Uzbekistan in the training of teachers of fine arts //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 420. – С. 10019.
20. Ibadullayeva S., Sunnatilloeva S. TASVIRIY SAN'AT DARSLARIDA NATYURMORT ISHLASH ORQALI O 'QUVCHILARNING IJODIY QOBILİYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE on

the topic: "Priority areas for ensuring the continuity of fine art education: problems and solutions". – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 01.

21. Ibadullayeva S. BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFLARDA TASVIRIY SAN'AT DARSLARINING MAZMUNIDA TARBIYA G 'OYASI //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE on the topic: "Priority areas for ensuring the continuity of fine art education: problems and solutions". – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 01.

22. Ibadullayevna I. S. BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA MATEMATIKA O'QITISHDA DARSDAN TASHQARI MASHG'ULOTLARNI TASHKIL ETISH METODIKASI //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 43. – №. 4. – С. 3-6.

23. Ikhamovna I. S. DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES IN FINE ARTS LESSONS //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 104-107.

24. Ikhamovna I. S. DEVELOPING CREATIVITY THROUGH THE USE OF NON-TRADITIONAL DRAWING TECHNIQUES //Formation and Development of Pedagogical Creativity: International Scientific-Practical Conference (Belgium). – 2023. – Т. 3. – С. 43-47.

25. Ибадуллаева Ш. И., Амонова Р. Ж. К. Коммуникативные Основы Художественной Культуры //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2022. – Т. 28. – С. 169-173.

26. Ibadullaeva S. I. The Role of Art in the Development of Junior Schoolchildren //European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 130-133.

27. Абдуллаев, С. С., Бакаев, Ш. Ш., Остонова, Г. Р., & Шарипов, Ш. Ш. (2021). Орнаментальная символика в народном декоративно-прикладном искусстве Бухары. *European science*, (2 (58)), 17-19.

28. Абдуллаев, Сухроб Сайфуллаевич. "ЭСТЕТИКА ЦВЕТА В ВОСПИТАНИИ ПЛАСТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ АРХИТЕКТОРА." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 1.1 (2022): 384-386.

29. Абдуллаев С. С., Шарипов Ш. Ш. ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА СТУДЕНТОВ СРЕДСТВАМИ НАРОДНОГО ДЕКОРАТИВНО-ПРИКЛАДНОГО ИСКУССТВА //XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TECHNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 80-85.